

VOLUNTARY ORGANIZATIONS AS SUBJECTS OF INTERNATIONAL LAW

Rasulov Bekzod Boymuratovich

doctor of philosophy in political sciences, independent researcher.

bekzodrasulov83@inbox.ru

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ABSTRACT

The legal foundations of volunteering were studied on the example of the international and national legal system in this article. International volunteer organizations, their directions of activity, as well as comments on improving the legal basis of volunteerism were analyzed.

Introduction

It was noted, that international organizations are independent entities of secondary international law. Their uniqueness is based on the absence of sovereign rights in international organizations. That is, the presence of territories and population is not required for international organizations. The legal will of international organizations is based on agreements between its members. States can conclude agreements with international organizations. It is also voluntary to join the documents of international organizations. International organizations are formed in different forms according to their areas of activity, territorial distribution and other characteristics. In the field of volunteerism, many such organizations were established in the 20th century. We can say that the structure of these organizations was firstly due to historical necessity, secondly due to the influence of international problems on people's consciousness and worldview, and

thirdly due to the increase of opportunities for communication between peoples. In particular, the consequences of the 2 world wars became a call to unify the world.

Voluntary activity is essentially a system that complements the activities of state authorities, contributes to the development and movement of aspects that are not paid attention by them, and at the same time performs important tasks that encourage government organizations to solve social problems in countries. is considered the growing importance of volunteerism in human society requires that it be reflected more deeply in the legislation of international organizations and national states.

Of course, today's level of development of volunteering has been formed on the basis of the rules of international organizations and states, which have a voluntary recommendation value or are mandatory for the member states of the organization. For this reason, there is a need to improve

the organizational and legal framework of this sector.

There is another important aspect of research work is that this issue has not been studied as a separate legal study in Central Asian countries. The legal system in this area is also relatively new.

About a century ago, international organizations began to organize voluntary activities in Europe and the Americas by joining various societies and associations, and legal bases were created in the legislation of national states. Voluntary activities organized as an international organization are being regulated by some conventions and declarations and by documents of recommendation value. There are aspects of volunteering that are not covered by international legal documents, and we believe that this issue should be studied legally.

The purpose of study.

Studying the legal bases of volunteering activities on the example of international organizations and Uzbekistan. Also, it is to promote proposals and comments on the prospects of the development of the industry in Uzbekistan.

Research method and object.

Systematic analysis, comparative methods were used in this research work.

The object of research is issues related to the development prospects of volunteer activities in foreign countries and Uzbekistan.

Research results and their discussion.

In the 20th century, there have been 2 world wars, droughts, mass diseases and other global climate changes caused by famine, poverty or homelessness as a result of wars,

violations of human rights, etc. created the need for protection. Although helping people on the basis of volunteering existed in the history of the world, now countries and peoples have started to acquire the skills to implement these actions by uniting into single organizations and associations.

One of the first steps in this regard is the development of the United Nations Volunteers Program (UNV) at the initiative of the United Nations. The program is a program that helps promote peace and development through volunteering around the world. Managed by the United Nations Development Program (UNDP), this program brings together qualified, highly motivated, well-informed professionals working in various UN agencies and promotes the values and global recognition of volunteerism.

In 2018, there were 7,201 UN Volunteers worldwide, 81 percent of whom came from the Global South. This program is directly responsible for the actual recruitment and placement of UN Volunteers who contribute their skills and talents to UN activities in the field, regional agencies and headquarters, while gaining professional UN experience.

The United Nations Volunteer Program (UNV) defines volunteering as: Volunteering is for students and professionals to solve important problems, educate themselves as global citizens, and develop useful skills. is a great opportunity. With their knowledge and passion, UN Volunteers contribute to the promotion of the goals and principles of the UN, as well as the principle of multilateralism and stability, through concrete practical work.

UNV (United Nations Volunteers) - UN Volunteers was established on December 7, 1970 at the initiative of the United Nations Development Program. United Nations

Volunteers (UNV) Program Through the United Nations, volunteering contributes to peace and development around the world. An organization directly subordinate to the UN, it is engaged in promoting sustainable global development on our planet by promoting the ideas of volunteerism and mobilizing volunteers to solve concrete practical problems on our planet. UN volunteers work with refugees, HIV patients, children, disabled people; working in child and adult education, health, urban planning, electoral law and voter rights protection, gender equality and women's rights, and other areas.

The Committee for Coordination of International Voluntary Service (CCIVS) is an INGO (international non-governmental organization) established in 1948 under the auspices of UNESCO. It is a global network dedicated to international voluntary service. Every year, it coordinates the activities of more than 200 volunteer organizations in 100 countries of the world and involves them in social projects supported by more than 30,000 volunteers. CCIVS has been responsible for the global coordination of the World Heritage Volunteers (WHV) initiative since 2008 and is also the regional coordinator for Africa, the Arab States, Latin America and the Caribbean.

SCI (Service Civil International) is an international volunteer organization founded in 1920 and has 33 branches around the world. Its tasks include promoting the ideas of peace, international solidarity, social justice and environmental protection. The main activity of SCI is to organize international volunteer projects, seminars, short, medium and long-term volunteer programs, educational training and international exchanges. SCI is a vehicle

for informal learning, a catalyst for change within individuals, and empowers people in communities to engage in meaningful, productive, and socially beneficial work as active members of society.

YAP - Youth Movement for Peace (www.yap.it) was founded in 1970 as an organization with international short-term volunteer projects (work camps), workshops, intercultural youth animators, medium-term and long-term organizes and implements training courses for the disabled. YAP volunteers organize anti-war projects, pacifist seminars and trainings, develop non-violent solutions to military conflicts, work with refugees, socially vulnerable groups, lobby anti-war and peace ideas among political parties and organizations. .

ICYE (International Cultural Youth Exchange) - ICYE federation started its activity in 1949. ICYE has more than 30 branches in Africa, Asia, Europe and Latin America. ICYE's mission is to promote youth volunteerism for international understanding and peace. An international non-profit youth exchange organization that provides opportunities for youth mobility, intercultural education and international volunteer services, helping people to overcome prejudice and develop intercultural understanding and skills for a more just and peaceful world. Global education and intercultural education are two main principles of ICYE programs for children, seniors and people with disabilities; organization of children's centers, on environmental projects. ICYE organizes long-term and short-term exchanges combining homestay and volunteer work in more than 40 countries around the world.

Alliance (Union of European Voluntary Service Organizations) - The European Voluntary Service Organizations Alliance, established in 1982, is the main center of European national voluntary organizations specializing in coordinating short and long-term volunteer work camps promoting international ideas. Currently, it unites 53 members from 31 countries of Europe, Asia and America. Each member organization implements an annual program of international volunteering projects in its country and exchanges volunteers with each other in accordance with the Alliance's Quality Charter. Every year, on average, 12,000 young volunteers participate in more than 1,200 social projects organized by branches.

AVSO (Association of Voluntary Service Organizations) - Founded in 1989, the Association of Voluntary Service Organizations coordinates the activities of European voluntary organizations and promotes the interests of volunteering at the level of governments, social institutions and community organizations. Its main activities are as follows:

- Development of charitable activities by promoting national and international voluntary service in Europe;
- conducting training sessions for voluntary service within the limits of their capabilities;
- Protecting and promoting national and international voluntary service in Europe, disseminating information about it and encouraging cooperation between voluntary organizations.

On September 14, 1990, at the XI World Conference of the International Association of Voluntary Efforts in Paris, the Universal Declaration of Volunteers was adopted, which defined the content, goals, and basic

principles of the movement. Accordingly, volunteers recognize and practice the following core principles:

- recognition of the right of association for all men, women and children;
- respecting the dignity and culture of all people, regardless of their race, religion, social and financial status, physical characteristics;
- the spirit of partnership and brotherhood, providing mutual assistance, free services, personally or organizationally;
- recognition of the equal importance of individual and collective needs, encouragement, collective provision of these needs;
- set the goal of turning volunteering into an element of personal well-being;
- to acquire new knowledge and skills, to improve abilities, to encourage people's initiative and creativity, to give everyone the opportunity to be a creator, not a user;
- to awaken in people a sense of family, community and international solidarity responsibility.

Based on these core principles, volunteers:

- help transform individual participation into collective action;
- actively support their associations, be loyal to their goals, be aware of their policies and activities;
- strive, based on one's capabilities and availability of free time, to act in accordance with assumed responsibilities until the successful completion of jointly developed programs;
- cooperation with colleagues in the association in the spirit of mutual understanding and mutual respect;
- not avoiding new knowledge;

NVDA (Network for Volunteer Development in Asia) is a network of International Volunteer Organizations (IVOs) NGOs in

Asia and Oceania. NVDA was founded in 1997 and currently has 30 NGO members in 20 countries/regions. We have created 1,949 IVS projects and shared 14,155 volumes. In 2015, IVS projects were launched in 17 new countries and are actively working on environmental or social synergies, development of PR (public relations) and LMTV (long-term and medium-term volunteer service), impact studies, etc. This organization funds and implements medium- and long-term sustainable community-based volunteer service projects with a special focus on women, children and minority groups.

From the time when volunteering began to develop widely, foreign countries began to develop their own legal norms related to the field. The European Center for Non-Commercial Law (ECNL) has published an overview of European practices in the regulation of volunteering. The analytical document "Volunteering - European regulatory practice" presented modern European approaches to the legal regulation of volunteer work. In particular, the document covers the legal status of the volunteer, the extension of labor guarantees and benefits to him, the need for social insurance, taxation issues and the need for clearly formed legal responsibility norms for volunteering, as well as problems related to international voluntary work.

The definition of volunteering given by the European Center for Volunteering in Brussels (Manifesto 2006) describes the activities of volunteers in a wider social context: "Volunteering is an activity in which:

- according to free will and self-motivation;
- free of charge;
- in an organized framework;

- it is understood to protect the interests of others and act in the interest of the whole society.

At the international level, the volunteer movement is represented by several large organizations, among which the International Association of Voluntary Efforts (IAVE) has a leading position. In the ideas of this organization, views on corporate volunteerism are analyzed. Corporate volunteering is a dynamic global force led by companies that want to make a meaningful contribution to solving serious global and local problems. Forms and means of corporate volunteering depend on cultural traditions. It was created in 1970 by a group of enthusiasts to promote the ideas of volunteerism and international exchange as a way to build trust and cooperation between people. The International Association for Volunteer Effort (IAVE) is the only global non-governmental organization dedicated to supporting and strengthening volunteerism around the world. Its members are organizations and individuals from different countries who promote and support the values of volunteerism.

In general, there are currently international legal and national legal problems that need to be solved in the field of volunteering. As mentioned above, the recommendation status played a greater role in the documents on volunteering adopted by international organizations and associations. Based on the content of these documents, it is appropriate to recognize the following legal issues in the field of volunteering:

- The documents adopted by the UN, International Labor Organization, UNESCO and a number of other international organizations do not contain norms

regarding the protection of labor rights of volunteers;

- The legal solution to the issue of taxing or not taxing volunteer activities has not been clarified;
- Contractual relations in volunteer activities have not been improved;
- In many countries, legal mechanisms for the development of volunteerism have been created in recent years. He has not yet reached his perfection.

Of course, every area in society will develop well only if it has its own legal pillars. At this point, some spheres of social life spread widely in people's lives and reach the level of etiquette. These rules then become legal rules. That is, the state expresses its legal force by passing laws on these provisions. The global pandemic, climate change, and environmental hazards that have occurred in recent years have made volunteering a rule of etiquette.

Legalization of volunteering within the framework of international organizations and national state legislation prevents many questions and misinterpretations that arise around this type of activity. Although its activity gives the impression that it is part of the activities of NGOs, it requires legal protection in view of the fact that this activity provides voluntary help to people, the main audience is young people, and in many cases their activity requires cooperation with state authorities. requires riding.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the legal basis for the development of this activity is being created in the following years. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Volunteer Activities" was adopted on December 2, 2019. With this law, the goals and tasks of volunteering, basic principles, forms and main directions of volunteering,

volunteering program, accounting for volunteering, state regulation of the field of volunteering, subjects of volunteering, relations in the field of volunteering, volunteering contracts, including issues such as encouragement and support of volunteer activities, financial provision. In this law, it is reflected that a contract should be drawn up regarding labor relations in voluntary activities only if more than 20 hours are engaged in 1 month.

Although this law on the legal regulation of volunteering activities and the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 11.04.2022 No. 169 "On measures to further support volunteering activities" have been adopted in our country, cannot fully cover the aspects of this field that should be regulated by other legal documents. That is, first of all, the Civil Code and the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan should include norms related to the regulation of volunteer activities. We believe that it is appropriate to include the relevant norms in the legislation on administrative responsibility in cases of preventing volunteer activities or prohibiting such activities without legal grounds.

Conclusions and suggestions.

Volunteering is becoming one of the areas of increasing importance in the world community due to its essence. The rapid spread of information about various global problems in the world causes people to come closer to each other, to seek voluntary help and to respond quickly. As a result, international volunteerism has become a code of ethics for people, and now it is a unique process for these relations to acquire a legal nature by itself and to improve.

Certain legal documents have been adopted by international organizations in the field of volunteering. These documents are in the form of conventions, declarations and similar forms, and their adherence is a recommendation for nations. International legal documents related to volunteer activities should be integrated with various fields of international law.

As a result of the implementation of volunteering in some areas, it is desirable to improve the legal mechanisms of the system of encouraging volunteers. In particular, young volunteers for doing work such as providing voluntary assistance to the activities of authorities, providing free vocational education or training to the

disabled, volunteering in educational institutions to teach languages or other subjects to children in the form of clubs. its promotion contributes positively to the increase of volunteerism among young people and the development of a positive living environment among society members.

It is expedient to introduce norms related to volunteerism in national legal documents related to labor, civil, tax and administrative procedures. We believe that the relations between the state power and local authorities, voluntary organizations and volunteers should be given a legal assessment.

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